

Employee's Selection and Organisation Performance in Norwegian People's Aid (NPA) Organisation

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Abstract

The study on Employee's selection process and organisation performance was guided by four research objectives were oriented towards determining the respondents profiles in terms of gender, age, level of education, type of employment and length of service, the level of employees selection process in NPA Juba southern Sudan, the level of organisation performance in NPA Juba Southern Sudan and establishing the relationship between employee's selection process and organisation performance in Juba southern Sudan. The study was guided by descriptive correlation research design, purposive and stratified sampling techniques were used in determining the appropriate sample sizes (180) respondent that were used for the study and a closed ended questionnaire was used in collecting data from the field. Concerning the relationship between the two-study variable, results from pearsons linear correlation coefficient revealed all existing employee selection practices are significantly correlated with all aspects of organizational performance in case of NPA (all sig. <0.05). Results also indicate that employee selection practices are positively correlated with all aspects of organizational performance in NPA (all r-values>0). This implies that an improvement in the selection procedures significantly improves organizational performance as per this study.

Keywords: *Employee's selection process, organisation performance, NPA, southern Sudan.*

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Introduction

Employee selection has remained a concern for a long time and as a result various recruitment and selection approaches have risen to address this problem. All these approaches are geared towards bringing in the organization a person with all the necessary competencies to perform the job efficiently. Selection plays a major role as it involves careful screening and testing of candidates who have put in their application for any job in the organization. This is necessary for two reasons. First, many of the candidates may not be qualified or experienced enough to work for the organization; second, even if all of the applicants are qualified and experienced, the organization may not have enough openings to accommodate them all. As a result, defining the attributes necessary for good job performance and then evaluating applicants based on those characteristics is part of the selection process. Knowing that recruiting and maintaining competent workers is one of the most challenging tasks, managers in organizations must design criteria that are appropriate in the selection process. Using Norwegian People's Aid (NPA) workers as a case study, this study will attempt to test both ideas on the link between personnel selection and organizational success. NPA is a non-governmental organisation providing services of vocational training, clearing land-mines and food security for the population in war ravaged areas especially in southern Sudan and has its head Quarters in Juba, Southern Sudan. Selection of candidates begins after the completion of the recruitment process. In other words, the process of selection begins only after an adequate number of applicants have been secured through different sources of recruitment-internal and or external. In this study the researcher examines selection of employees of Norwegian People's Aid (NPA) and it will be conceptualized as those things managers do which propel others into action or that creates an environment in which people want to work to their full potential. Selection refers to selecting the right candidate for the job. Is the process by which an organization chooses from a list of applicants the person or persons who best meet the selection criteria for the position available, considering current environment condition. Since its creation in 1997, in Southern Sudan, the performance of Norwegian People's Aid (NPA), which is often exhibited in performance of its employees and volunteers, has been a big question in the mind set of very many Southern Sudanese. The performance of NPA employees is often questioned on a number of aspects and this study will examine it in terms of attendance at work, time management, innovation, fairness, task accomplishment, quality of work, customer care, performance appraisal, team work, problem solving. The Government of Sothern Sudan has improved the livelihood of its people with the support and help from a number of non-government organizations (NGOs); however, NPA constitutes the largest or remarkable contribution/share; such aid in form of grant from government in financing its national budget. The aid given by NPA to developing countries like Sothern Sudan is in line with its vision which stresses society where people have equal opportunities, a global society based on justice and respect between individuals, ethnic group and nations. The employees of NPA find the basis for it national and international activity in those values that have underpinned the existence and activities of the organization for more than fifty years (50). These values are summed up in the concepts-unity, solidarity and human dignity, but also find basis in the concepts of freedom, peace, equality and brotherhood. These same values formed the foundation for development of the social democratic ideology and policies in Europe, form the European interwar period until today – an ideology that among other things has fostered the evolution of the Nordic welfare states. Under the human resource policy of NPA, emphasis is geared towards the creation of stable and predictable work force, equip them with skills strengthen their competencies, control and increase their productivity (Various NPA reports). Besides those values, the pending question is whether NPA is performing to the expectations of the government and the people of Sothern Sudan.

In some years ago after the creation of NPA, there was a remarkable shortfall in the performance of the organization and this might be attributed to the shortage of enough human resource base with in the Country (Southern Sudan). A number of skills are lacking with in the country and this compels the organization to recruit anybody since the laws of the country require such organizations to give priority to nationals. This is worsened by many government officials who always interfere with the operations of such organization within the country by influencing them to recruit their relatives even though they lack qualifications to perform such tasks. Consequently, the performance of NPA started declining slowly and people's trust in the organization started declining. Secondly, this has seriously compromised government's efforts to improve the livelihood of the national subsequently putting pressure on NPA to improve on the efficiency of its selection process. NPA staff performance is paramount as Southern Sudanese government and NPA management try to improve on the livelihood of the people, through the implementation of a long-term development projects as well as emergency aid; not forgetting mine clearing activities. However, over the years, the progress of the activities has declined due to unprofessional recruitment and selection system which has led to staff frustrations, lack of recognition, poor communication, and lack of cooperation, poor time management, continued absenteeism, deadlines failed targets and substandard work output due to incompetence of recruits. For example, some ministers and government officials influence the personnel department to offer jobs to their relatives irrespective of their academic qualification, some officials practice nepotism and ask for bribe from applicants in order to be offered jobs in the organization leaving qualified and competent candidates aside, at times they go ahead and duplicate some positions and routine work, with little room for creativity. This has resulted in a lot of mistakes, resource wastage, accidents at work place, redundancy, poor customer care, low morale, and increased corruption cases as reported in the media, consequently leading to poor performance or failure to meet targets. Therefore, researcher suggests that if the selection process of NPA staff is improved, it would greatly help the organization realize its vision. Therefore, it is against this background that the researcher seeks to explore the relationship between employee selection and Organization performance in NPA. Basically, the study investigated relationship between employee selection and organization performance in Norwegian people's Aid (NPA) organization Juba Southern Sudan. Thus, the general objective of the study is to determine the relationship between employee selection process and organization performance in Norwegian People's Aid (NPA) - Juba Southern Sudan. We also investigated the following objectives: (1) To determine the relationship between employee skills and organization performance. (2) To determine the relationship between employee application forms procedures and organization performance. (3) To determine relationship between employee preliminary interview, experience, knowledge and organization performance. & (4) To establish the relationship between employee's selection process and Organization performance in NPA Southern Sudan Juba. Specially we want to get answers of the following research questions (i) Is there a relationship between employee skills and organization performance? (ii) Is there a relationship between employee application forms procedures and organization performance? (iii) Is there a relationship between employee preliminary interview, experience, and knowledge and organization performance? & (iv) Is there a significant relationship between employee's selection process and organization performance in NPA Juba Southern Sudan? The following disciplines would benefit from the findings of the study. The research findings are likely to help the management of NPA by providing a more realistic approach to selection process of employees which do not only focus on attracting competent employees from external labour market but also retains the ones that are already serving in it. Additionally, the results of the study are likely to be useful to future researchers who might be interested in conducting research in areas of selection and organizational performance. This is because they might use

this thesis as a point of reference when reviewing their related studies. Finally, The study is also likely to assist both private and public policy makers in southern Sudan when drafting selection policies that often act as continuing guidelines on the approach that management follow when weeding out unwanted candidates from the pool of potential applicant after recruitment.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Employee Selection

Employee selection refers to the process of selecting the best candidates from a pool of candidates, or the process of matching applicants' credentials to job criteria (Gary, 2005). It is the process of selecting the best candidate for the position from a pool of candidates that answered to the company's job posting. Employee selection was defined in this study as a process that encompasses a number of steps such as filling out application forms, conducting interviews, formal testing, reference checking, physical examination, and making final selection decisions (Sattinger, 1993, in Maicibi, 2007).

Employee application forms

Individuals seeking employment (applicants) must fill out application forms to advise employers of their qualifications and willingness to work for a certain position (Diane, 1998). Filling up application forms is the first phase in the selection process, and it entails candidates providing necessary personal information such as qualifications, specializations, and experience, among other things (Jain & Saakshi, 2008). This approach allows the company to choose which applicants will be invited in for interviews. The information on application forms is used to determine if an applicant fits the minimal requirements for experience, education, and other factors (Schuler, 1995). Candidates are sometimes needed to fill out blank application forms, which operate as application forms and contain data about the candidates, such as their age.

Employment/Job Interviews

A job interview is the process of interviewing someone (in this example, a job application) in order to ascertain whether or not they are qualified for a specific post (Armstrong, 2009). There are two types of job interviews: preliminary interviews and follow-up interviews.

Preliminary interview

Preliminary interviews, also known as screening interviews, are intended to select out individuals who do not fulfill the organization's basic standards (Prasad, 2007; Ivancevich, 2001). Preliminary interview procedures, it has been argued, are the most important means of evaluating applicants' appearance, and they are used to establish friendly relationships between applicants and the company, as well as to obtain additional information or clarification on information in the application form (Jain & Saakshi, 2008). Final interviews are more regimented and scheduled, whereas preliminary interviews are less so. The candidates are given a brief overview of the organization and the job description, as well as an assessment of their knowledge of the company (Ivancevich, 2001).

Final Interviews for selection

Final selection interviews are a type of in-depth interview in which applicants are carefully questioned on both technical and behavioral characteristics (Prasad, 2007; Ivancevich, 2001). In today's workplaces, most job interviews are centered on this sort of interview method, in which technical or behavioral exams are utilized to screen out individuals who do not qualify or are not a priority (Prasad, 2007). Final selection interviews are the ideal methods for picking

the highest performing individuals for a business in light of this perspective (Jain & Saakshi, 2008).

Formal employment testing procedures

Formal employment tests are evaluation checks used later in the selection process to examine the nature, qualities and talents, likes and dislikes, intellect, capacity to learn and profit from training, and adaptability of the selected workers (Jain & Saakshi, 2008). According to Jain and Saakshi, there are several sorts of tests that may be undertaken in this quest (2008) include; a) Intelligence test (used to determine one's alertness, reasoning ability, and power of comprehension by reading, summarizing, naming in a few minutes, adding in a few minutes, and so on); b) Performance or achievement tests (used to determine one's level of knowledge and skills in a particular area by performing a simple operation similar to the proposed job, such as driving, typing, or attending to a prospective customer); c) Aptitude test (used to determine one's (used to measure personality characteristics like self-confidence, integrity, originality and others).

Medical examination

According to Bakinson (2008), a medical examination is a procedure or test performed by a health care professional to obtain information about a person's physical or mental status. Examples of medical examinations include vision tests, blood tests, breath analyses, blood pressure screening, X-ray scans, and many others. The medical test verifies that the applicants' health meets the work requirements (Sherman, Bohlander & Snell, 1998). Medical examinations are performed to confirm that the potential employee is physically fit. Performance, workers' compensation claims, and absenteeism are all predicted by medical exams. It serves as a benchmark against which subsequent medical examinations can be compared and interpreted in order to establish if work-related impairments are covered under worker's compensation law.

A referee.

According to Jain & Saakshi (2008), a referee is a person who serves as a possible source of information regarding a candidate's skills and personality.

Reference Checks.

A reference check is the process of contacting the applicant's referral listed on the application letter/form in order to learn more about the applicant and verify the accuracy of the information supplied on the application form (Jain & Saakshi, 2008). It is completed prior to the employer making a final decision based on the references provided by the candidate in the application form. The company may also look at the candidate's previous job history, education, personal reputation, financial situation, and criminal history. If the information is correct, reference checking aids in forecasting performance.

Final approval

In most organizations, the human resource department is in charge of the selection process, and the department's judgments are advisory. The department's short-listed applicants are eventually authorized by the executive of the department or unit in question. Employment is provided in the form of an appointment letter that details the position, rank, salary grade, start date, and other terms and conditions. In certain organizations, both the applicant and the organization's representative sign the contract of services. As Graham says, it is at this stage that a selected candidate is treated with a letter of offer for a job, and the initial offer of a position requires extra attention, particularly in terms of confidentiality: (a) The wage or

compensation given must be not only acceptable for the position and appealing to candidates, but also comparable to current employee salaries. (b) The position must be specified, and any specific requirements must be stated. For example, you will be trained in the head office for the first year, and subsequently moved to upcountry branches. (c) Candidates must be aware of the fundamental job circumstances, such as working hours, vacations, bonuses, and fringe benefits. (d) All terms and conditions must be specified, such as that your employment will be contingent on adequate references and medical examinations. Generally, applicants are hired on a probationary basis for one or two years, after which they are confirmed in their position if they perform well during that time.

Notify the top candidate.

After being hired, the candidate should be contacted and given the opportunity to accept the employment. If the top applicant declines the post, the second-best candidate, if qualified, might be considered for the position. After the individual who has been given the position accepts it, the other candidates should be told in writing or by phone (Roselius & Kleiner, 2000).

Induction

Induction is the process of welcoming new employees to the firm, introducing them to their coworkers, and telling them about the company's operations, customers, and traditions (Graham, page 219, 1998). At this point, new recruits are given several induction courses in order to acclimate them to their new working environment. In Sudan, for example, the practice is highly valued in public service, with a number of secular publications devoted to the subject.

Follow-up (evaluation)

According to Graham, all selections should be verified by follow-up, which is a step in which workers are asked how they feel about their development so far, and their immediate supervisors are asked for comments, which are compared to the notes obtained during the selection interviews. If the results of the follow-up are unfavorable, it's probable that the selection was flawed. The whole process, from job descriptions through interviews, was examined to determine whether a better option might be made next time. Also, Prasad (2005, p. 249) said that, while evaluation is not strictly a stage in the selection process, it aids in assuring efficacy by attempting to assess the reliability and validity of various phases utilized in the process.

Organizational performance

Draft (1997) defines an organization as a social entity that is goal-oriented and consciously organized, and performance as the capacity of the organization to achieve its goals via efficient and effective resource use. Similarly, Bates and Holton (1995) describe performance as a multi-dimensional concept that is measured differently based on a range of criteria. The degree to which a task that makes up an organization's objectives is completed is referred to as organizational performance (Leslie Rue et al, 2000). It demonstrates how well an organization is meeting the Job's criteria. Organizational performance, according to Kanter (2009), is defined as an organization's actual output or outcomes as compared to its expected outputs (or goals and objectives). Employee performance has been used to analyze an organization's success on multiple occasions since, in many cases, an organization's performance is achieved via its employees. Employee performance is evaluated in this study based on regularity, originality, and creativity, coordination, customer service, job completion, timekeeping, quality maintenance, number of customers serviced, loan recovery, and report production. These indicators have a role in the aims and goals that an organization like NPA aspires to attain. As

a result, this study examined the extent to which employees aid their business in achieving these goals.

Theoretical Perspectives

This research was guided by the job matching theory proposed by Sattinger (1993) and cited in Maicibi (2007), which states that depending on the characteristics of the job, different characteristics of workers such as educational background, skills, knowledge and experience, or other types of competence when sieving competent employees from a pool of potential applicants is recommendable and will yield results in the future, and the quality of the match or the fit between the two is important and will yield results in the future, and the quality of the match or the fit between. The theory was accepted by the researcher because it highlights the concept of work fit, which means that when hiring personnel, the focus should be on individual traits that meet the job needs a good fit also leads to better productivity and excellent performance. Because of the expense of educating the applicants, the cost of mistakes made by the candidates, and the cost of replacement, a bad match is tremendously costly to the organization (Daft, 2000).

Employee application forms procedure and organizational performance

The performance of individuals who are chosen is projected to improve as a result of the efficient conduct and security of application forms. Employee performance issues such as absenteeism, turnover, and inefficiency would be minimized if application forms are carefully inspected, according to Jain & Saakshi, (2008). Critically examining workers' qualifications, specializations, and experiences is likely to attract good employees and eliminate bad ones, as people with faulty documents and inabilities are likely to be eliminated during this process, and in the end, a highly competent workforce is likely to be employed for the organization's efficiency. The process of picking the best workers by employing application forms aids in the selection of individuals with suitable abilities, education, and experience, resulting in great performance of the selected employees (Diane, 1998). Employees must declare their relevant talents, experiences, and abilities, as well as their academic papers, on their application forms. This enables managers to select individuals with the most appropriate talents for the task, resulting in a high-performing group of employees. An individual's work performance, according to Dawson (1996), is a reflection of motivation, ability, technical, and social environment. High levels of organizational performance, according to Thompson & Strickland (1995), Harrison (1997), and Armstrong (2000), are founded on a clear grasp of the organization's mission, strategies, and goals. Many elements, according to Armstrong (2000), contribute to organizational performance, including: I) Clearly defined objectives and strategies for achieving them; II) A value system that prioritizes performance, capability, productivity, equity, customer service, teamwork, and flexibility; III) Constant pressure to innovate and grow; IV) Ability to respond quickly to opportunities and threats; V) A well-motivated, skilled, and flexible workforce; and VI) Strong visionary leadership from the top management team.

Preliminary interview and organizational performance

According to Prasad (2007), missing preliminary interviews is not only a terrible idea, but it may also be harmful for all parties involved; preparatory interviews minimize questions in the final interview and enhance applicant morale and confidence. It's actually a training phase, since employees go back and prepare, increasing their job competence in the process. Before additional time and money is wasted, they determine who can afford the job and who cannot. As a result, the most appropriate individuals who can perform to the standards are chosen. Preliminary interviews are frequently referenced in management texts, particularly those on

human resource management, although actual research on their impact is rare, if they exist at all. The current study attempted to contribute to this body of information by conducting a survey on the influence of such interviews on the performance of those chosen workers.

Final selection interviews and organizational performance

According to Katherine (2009), interview questions should be connected to the work and should test levels of competence, which can lead to the selection of high-performing individuals. Katherine demonstrates how important the quality of the interview questions is (e.g., are they too easy, too hard, biased, confusing, or inaccurate?). This is significant because, as Vique-Ocean (2010) argues, employees grow and/or strengthen their abilities and competencies as they prepare for these thorough, behavioral, and technical interviews, allowing them to gain confidence. Those who pass the interview gain confidence, patience, and honesty, all of which are important for an employee's increased performance (Vique-Ocean, 2010). While it is true that these interviews allow businesses to assess attributes such as rapid thinking, calmness, and coolness, which are sometimes required for the completion of certain jobs, it is also true that such persons may not be available without such interviews. According to Katherine (2009), these interviews allow employees to assess potential employees' technical skills as well as the attributes that distinguish them as exceptional performers. According to <http://www.businessballs.com/interview.htm>, effective job interview processes and procedures improve the quality of personnel in a company, but poor job interview methods result in poor selection, which weakens organizational performance. While all of this material focuses on final selection interviews, it lacks empirical support for employee performance levels and other factors relevant to this study, a gap that the researcher hopes to overcome.

Formal employment testing procedures and organizational performance

A successful performance test leads to the selection of high-performing individuals, which has an impact on the performance and productivity of the company. Hiring the wrong individuals is a waste of time, money, and business opportunity. Employment tests, if carefully selected, prepared, and given, may supply a company with employees who have the skills to function successfully on the job, lowering turnover and unproductive behavior. Individuals who are better matched to roles for which they are suited and will prefer to remain benefit from testing as well. Some tests, such as cognitive ability assessments, help to provide reliable inferences for performance and success, predict performance, particularly for complicated occupations, are cost effective, and are not easily influenced by the testing administrator (SIOP Inc., 2009). Studies such as those conducted by Viswesvaran & Schmidt (1993) and Sackett & Wanek (1996) discovered a link between integrity ratings and worker performance. However, they argue that exams must be relevant to the work and fair in order to have a meaningful influence on performance (Rosse, Ringer, & Miller, 1996; Rynes & Connerley, 1996). (1993). As a result, integrity tests with a good format and scale produce high results.

Employee Medical examination and organizational Performance

A well-conducted exam results in the selection of physically fit staff, who will perform better. Whether the test assesses an employee's execution of a task measures his or her physiological reactions to doing the work is one of the elements to examine in a medical examination, according to the US EEOC (2008). As a result, it is expected that firms that use efficient and relevant physical or medical examinations in their selection methods would hire higher-performing employees, which is what every company wants. However, it is difficult to show a correlation between a clear Physical or medical examination technique and employee performance, but it is necessary if managers and workers are to place greater weight on these

procedures. As a result, a study like this one, which aims to show a link between physical or medical examination methods and employee performance, is right on time.

Reference Checking Procedures and organizational Performance

According to Jain and Saakshi (2008), a referee is a potentially crucial source of information about a candidate's skill and personality, and it is done prior to the employer making a final decision based on the referees provided by the applicant in the application form. The company also looks at the candidate's previous work history, education, personal reputation, financial situation, and criminal history. If the information is correct, reference checking aids in forecasting performance. Reference checks, according to the Tourism HR Society (2010), assist to verify information on application forms and provide deeper insight into an applicant's skills, knowledge, and talents from someone who has actually witnessed a candidate perform. However, the relevance, application, and influence of reference checks in the selection process are all debatable. This introduces the concept that reference check inquiries should be relevant to the profession and one's life in a certain company, rather than one's personal life at home. Reference checks, if well-organized and executed, may be one of the best predictors of future performance, since they allow the employer to speak with previous superiors to see if the candidate is a good fit for the job. Despite all of these facts concerning the necessity of physical or medical examinations and reference-checking processes, research examining their influence on selected employees' performance are still lacking, particularly in the context of the workplace.

Impact of Employee Selection and organizational Performance

In any company, selection is a crucial function. The selection methods determine whether an organization succeeds or fails. According to Kreitner (1995), selection should be adequately screened to ensure that personnel have not only the requisite abilities, but also the necessary traits for the job. According to Williams (2002), the efficiency of an organization is closely tied to the caliber of its personnel. Because of the legal ramifications of poor hiring, effective selection is critical. Nondiscriminatory selection practices for protected groups are required by employment regulations and court rulings. In addition, courts will hold companies accountable if workers with criminal histories or other issues use access to customers' homes or other comparable possibilities to perpetrate crimes. Hiring personnel with such histories without sufficient safeguards, according to lawyers. According to the Harvard Business Review, improper recruiting decisions account for 80% of turnover. These are costly errors, with money spent on recruiting, selection, and training, as well as expenses associated with lower production when other employees step in to fill the void (Meyer, 2009). According to Kreitner (1995), properly selecting personnel is more crucial than ever, since it serves as the organization's human resource gatekeeper. Managers now face a difficult task: finding the greatest possible talent while not discriminating against any group of people.

Factors which hinder effective employee's selection

Human resource professionals frequently make mistakes when selecting personnel, and as a result of bad selection judgments, organizations encounter issues such as employee theft of money or property, high employee turnover, and low productivity, to name a few. According to the Harvard Business Review, improper recruiting decisions account for 80% of turnover. These are costly errors, with money spent on recruiting, selection, and training, as well as expenses associated with lower production when other employees step in to fill the void (Meyer, 2009). According to Kreitner (1995), properly selecting personnel is more crucial than ever, since it serves as the organization's human resource gatekeeper. Managers now face a difficult task: finding the greatest possible talent while not discriminating against any group of

people. Interviewers frequently have a variety of biases that have a significant impact on their judgments of certain job seekers. Interviewers and supervisors, despite their best intentions, have an instinctive propensity to favor persons who are similar to themselves (Meyer, 2009). According to Williams (2002), all selection methods must be verified in order to discover how effectively a test or procedure predicts future job performance. Accurate selection tests are a critical tool in assisting firms in avoiding the expenses of poor performance, as well as ensuring that employees are hired in legally authorized ways (Ivancevich, Zorenzi, Skinner, Crosby, 1994).

Hypothesis development

Relationship between Employee Selection and Organisational Performance

Selection is an important function as no organisation can achieve its goals without selecting the right people, where faulty in selection leads to wastage of time, money and spoils the environment of an organisation (Prasad, 2005). In this regards, scientific selection and placement of personnel can go a long way in building up a stable work force, where it helps to reduce absenteeism and labour turnover at the same time very helpful in increasing the efficiency and productivity of the enterprise (Dessler, 2005). Interviewers often have a range of biases that dramatically affect their perceptions of individual job candidates. Despite the best of intentions, interviewers and supervisors have an unconscious tendency to favor people who are similar to themselves (Meyer, 2009). Kreitner (2004) noted that, interviewers of job applicants require polished administrative and interpersonal skills to meet the needs of an increasingly diverse workforce. Failure to validate selection procedure is another challenge problem which faces many organizations. Williams, (2002) noted that, it is important that all selection procedures be validated in order to determine how well a selection test or procedure predicts future job performance. Accurate selection tests are a major tool in helping organizations avoids the costs of poor performance, they also help to ensure that an organization is hiring people in legally acceptable (Ivancevich, Zorenzi, Skinner, Crosby, 1994). Mkhize, Zakhele, Denzil, (2007) noted that, existing literature and studies revealed that the selection and appointment process in some organization is fraught with many problems. Some of the problems originate from the nature and the way the selection committee is composed. Subsequently, their ability to interview and select employees is questionable. The findings of the study suggested that there are also underlying factors which affected the selection process. These factors ranged from favoritism, subjectivity and biasness, selection and scoring criteria, lack of expertise to manipulation by members during the selection process. Thus, we develop the following hypothesis

H1: There is no significant relationship between employee's selection process and organization performance in NPA Southern Sudan Juba.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive correlation research design was used in this study. This study approach aided the researcher in gathering the impressions and opinions of field respondents, which were then utilized to thoroughly characterize the phenomena under question. Furthermore, the researcher was able to demonstrate a link between the selection procedure and organization performance in NPA Southern Sudan Juba using a descriptive correlation research methodology.

Research Population

The target population included a total of 180 respondents from top, middle and lower level management as categorized in table 1 below.

Table 1: Category of Respondents

Number	Category of respondents	Target population	Sample size
1	Top managers	21	19
2	Middle level managers	57	42
3	Lower level employees	102	63
	Total	180	124

Source: Payroll July, 2011.

Sample Size

The sample size was 150 responders from NPA's top, middle, and lower management levels. The sample size was calculated using Sloven's formula, which is listed below.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n= Sample size, N=Target population and e = level of significance at 0.05.

Sampling Procedures

Stratified and purposive sampling techniques were used in selecting suitable respondents for the study.

Research Instruments

Only closed ended questionnaires with likert scale were given to selected sampled respondents in order to obtain suitable and genuine data for the study.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

The researcher devised questionnaires on employee selection and organization performance were subjected to the content expert's method proposed by Gay (1996), which estimates the validity on the basis of their experience) such as professors, associate professors, and senior lecturers in educational management, to ensure content validity. As a result, the researcher modified the materials in accordance with the expert's advice. Furthermore, the researcher improved the research instrument's reliability by piloting the questionnaires prior to actual data collection, resulting in discoveries from piloted respondents, particularly in the questionnaire's wording, the chronology used in drafting the instrument, and the language used. All of this was taken into account by the researcher, and required modifications were made, resulting in a more trustworthy questionnaire throughout and after the survey.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before the administration of the questionnaires

The researcher received an introduction letter from the School of Postgraduate Studies and Research, which he used to ask the heads of departments for permission to conduct the study. After receiving approval, the researcher obtained a list of eligible respondents from the head of the organization in charge and used stratified and purposive sampling procedures to pick acceptable respondents.

Data Analysis

The information was acquired, entered into a computer, and statistically analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive means statistics computed using the

SPSS software were used to determine the level of selection process in NPA Southern Sudan Juba and the level of organization performance in NPA Southern Sudan Juba, respectively. The calculated mean value was interpreted using the Likert scale shown below.

Range	Response Mode	Interpretation
1.00- 1.75	strongly Disagree	Very low
1.76- 2.5	Disagree	Low
2.56-3.25	Agree	Moderate
3.26-4.00	strongly agree	High

Pearson's linear correlation coefficient (PLCC, r) was used in establishing whether there is any significant relationship between Selection process and organization performance in NPA Southern Sudan Juba

Ethical Considerations

The following actions were carried out by the researcher to protect the confidentiality of the information supplied by the respondents and to assure the practice of ethics in this study: Through a formal approach to the NPA organization, request permission to use the standardized questionnaire on staff selection and organizational performance. Instead of reflecting the names, the responders in the organization were coded. The study includes obtaining authorization through a formal request to the organization's responsible officials. Solicit signatures on the Informed Consent Form from the respondents (Appendix 3) Authors were acknowledged in this study, as well as the author of the standardized instrument, using citations and references. The results were presented in a broad sense.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

Description of respondents

Employees of the NPA Juba - Southern Sudan program were among those who took part in the survey. The primary goal of this research was to see if there was a link between employee talents and company performance. Using a closed-ended questionnaire, employees of NPA in Juba were requested to supply us with their technical skills, experience, and knowledge, as well as their profile in connection to their organization's performance. As shown in table 2, their replies were examined using frequencies and percentage distributions.

Table 2: Respondents' Profile

Categories	Frequency	Percent
Sex		
Male	90	60
Female	60	40
Total	150	100
Age group		
Below 30 years	40	27
30-40 years	70	47
41-50 years	20	13
Above 50 years	20	13
Total	150	100
Education level		
Certificate	30	20
Diploma	40	27
Degree	70	47
Masters	10	7
Total	150	100
Employment status		
Contract	90	60
Permanent	30	20
Probation	30	20
Total	150	100

Position		
Manager	5	4
Administrator	8	5
Employee	137	91
Total	150	100
Years of service		
Below 5 years	135	90
5-9 years	15	10
Total	150	100

Table 2 shows that the majority of responders (60%) were men, while women accounted for just 40%. This reveals a gender divide in the allocation of NPA jobs in Juba. This imbalance may be attributed to women's inferiority, since few of them pursue schooling to qualify for such positions, resulting in a job market disparity. In terms of age, the majority of respondents (47 percent) were between the ages of 30 and 40, followed by those under 30 (27 percent), meaning that the majority of employees are teenagers and young adults. This is because most NGOs, such as NPA, like to hire young people who are still active and adaptable. NPA employs a majority of graduates (47 percent), diploma holders (27 percent), and certificate holders, according to the data (20 percent). There were just a handful of them who had master's degrees (7 percent). This implies that NPA's personnel have an acceptable level of education. Employees with such education are sought after by multinational organizations such as NPA because they are more productive. In terms of job status, 60% of NPA employees are on contract, 20% are on probation, and just 20% are permanent employees. This shows that NPA is a short-term NGO with short-term goals to fulfill before ceasing operations in the nation, hence there is no need for a large number of permanent staff. The survey sample was likewise dominated by employees (almost 91 percent) and relatively few supervisors, according to the findings. This is feasible because firms have fewer managerial roles, and even those who do exist are difficult to reach for data gathering reasons. Finally, the majority of NPA workers have worked there for less than five years, according to the findings (90). Our explains why, as previously stated in this study, the majority of NPA personnel are on contract or probation. Only those who have worked for more than five years on a permanent basis are eligible.]

Extent of existing Employee selection practices in NPA.

Employee selection procedures used in the NPA Juba - Southern Sudan program were the independent variable in this study, and the fourth objective was to determine the relationship between employee selection practices and NPA organization performance, for which the researcher wanted to know how satisfactory these practices are. Employee selection methods were divided into seven categories: i) Employee application forms procedure; ii) Preliminary interviews; iii) Final selection interviews; iv) Formal employment testing; v) Physical examination; vi) Reference Checking; and vii) Final approval. All the seven employee selection practices were measured using qualitative questions in the questionnaire, with each question Likert scaled using five points, where 1= strongly agree ; 2 = agree; 3=neutral; 4 = disagree; and 5 = strongly disagree. Employees were asked to assess how satisfied they were with each item by indicating how much they agreed with it. A respondent was asked to check a number that corresponded to their best option and thought process. As shown in tables 3A and 3B below, their replies were analyzed using SPSS and summarized using means.

Table 3A Extent of Existing Employee Selection Practices in NPA

Employee application forms selection procedure	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
The job application form you filled asked for your experience.	4.10	Unsatisfactory	1
The job application form you filled asked for your specialization	3.75	Unsatisfactory	2
The items of the form were relevant to my job.	3.67	Unsatisfactory	3
The job application form you filled asked for your qualifications.	3.47	Unsatisfactory	4
The job application forms asked for time you are available.	2.53	Satisfactory	5
The job application form you filled asked for your abilities.	2.17	Satisfactory	6
All new coming employees in NPA must fill application blanks.	1.87	Satisfactory	7
You believe your application forms were scrutinized fairly	1.73	Very satisfactory	8
You filled a job application form to access this job.	1.67	Very satisfactory	9
Sub Total	2.77	Fairly Satisfactory	
Preliminary interviews selection procedure			
In NPA the screening interviews they asked about company profile.	4.63	Very unsatisfactory	1
In NPA the screening interviews they asked about your job profile.	4.37	Very unsatisfactory	2
The questions in screening interviews were related to your job	4.07	Unsatisfactory	3
You did a screening interview before you accessed this job.	3.27	Unsatisfactory	4
The screening interviews examined your appearance.	2.00	Satisfactory	5
Sub Total	3.67	Unsatisfactory	
Final selection interviews			
The final interviews you did were only written.	4.70	Very unsatisfactory	1
The questions in final interviews you did were very easy.	4.60	Very unsatisfactory	2
You believe the final interviews you did were fair.	4.47	Very unsatisfactory	3
The final interviews you did were telephone based.	4.43	Very unsatisfactory	4
The final interviews you did examined your technical abilities.	4.13	Unsatisfactory	5
Questions in the final interview were related to your job.	3.90	Unsatisfactory	6
The final interviews you did were both written and oral.	3.87	Unsatisfactory	7
You did a file selection interview before you accessed this job.	3.87	Unsatisfactory	8
The questions in final interviews you did were clear & accurate	1.97	Satisfactory	9
The final interviews you did were individual based.	1.80	Very satisfactory	10
The final interviews you did were face-to-face and panel based.	1.60	Very satisfactory	11
The final interviews you did were only oral.	1.58	Very satisfactory	12
The questions in final interviews you did were very hard.	1.57	Very satisfactory	13
Sub Total	3.27	Fairly Satisfactory	

Key:**Rating Scale****Answer Range****Response mode****Interpretation**

1.00-1.80

strongly agree

Very satisfactory

1.81-2.60

Agree

Satisfactory

2.61-3.40

neutral

Fairly Satisfactory

3.41-4.20

Disagree

Unsatisfactory

4.21-5.00

strongly disagree

Very unsatisfactory

Table 3A shows that four components or aspects of the employee application forms practice or method are poor (means ranging from 4.10 to 3.47), all of which fall within the unsatisfactory response category. The issue of experience (mean=4.10) is the most disappointing component of employee application forms practice, followed by inquiries about specialities (mean=3.75). This indicates that employees believe the practice is either irrelevant or not carried out in a fair and fulfilling manner. Three features, however, were regarded as good, and two were ranked as quite satisfactory (with means ranging 2.53 - 1.67). Questions about available time (mean=2.53), abilities (mean=2.17), and the need that all new forthcoming workers fill out an application blank form (mean = 1.87) are among the aspects that were judged satisfactory. The component of the application forms method that was the most satisfying was that every employee contacted completed an application form before starting their present work (mean = 1.67). To gain a sense of how employees regarded the process of filling out application forms,

a mean for all nine components was calculated and found to be 2.77, which falls into the "pretty good" category on the rating scale. This means that the NPA's application form procedures are generally good. Only one component of the process of preliminary interviews was deemed good, while the rest were deemed unsatisfactory or extremely unsatisfactory. The only component of preliminary interviews that was good was that screening interviews looked at their looks (mean=2.00). The practice of preliminary interviews in NPA was assessed as bad overall, with a mean score of 3.67. This suggests that either this technique does not exist in NPA at all, or that it does exist but is rarely used, and when it is, it is exceedingly superficial, unjust, and irrelevant. Only four things were judged good or very satisfactory in final selection interviews, with nine items rated unsatisfactory or very unsatisfactory. The most unpleasant component of this study was the written interviews (mean=4.70), whereas the most satisfying aspect was the fact that the final interviews were extremely difficult (mean=1.57). Overall, the final selection interviews were regarded as reasonably good (overall mean=3.27), showing that NPA uses final selection interviews fairly in their personnel selection process. Employees in NPA assessed formal employment testing processes as poor (overall mean=4.12), according to the second portion of table 3 (table 3B). On official employment testing, all areas were graded as unsatisfactory or extremely unsatisfactory. The relevance of the selection tests (mean=4.48) is the most unpleasant element, followed by the fact that most workers did not take the selection exams (mean=4.47), and so on. This means that either this selection process does not exist in NPA, or if it does, it is used in an ineffective or unjust manner, suggesting a need for change. The results also show that the medical examination in NPA is done satisfactorily (overall mean=2.30).

The most disappointing part of medical examination processes at NPA, however, was the fitness test (mean=3.87), implying that fitness tests are not performed at NPA, according to the selected employees. The disability test (mean=1.63) is the most satisfied component of the medical examinations system, showing that most workers are given disability tests or examinations before they are hired at NPA. This is because such tests are simple to carry out. They can also do it through observation, in which a potential employee is observed to see whether he or she has any physical or mental disabilities. Reference checking was considered inadequate as well (overall mean = 3.97). However, one of the two aspects of this approach was assessed as very good, while the other was ranked as extremely bad. The worst objection (mean=4.33) was to whether workers' references were called before they were eventually picked, showing that contacting referees for job seekers in NPA is not deemed necessary. However, the data show that applicants are required to give referees in certain situations (mean=3.60) before they can access their positions, but that most referees are not contacted for extra information about the applicants' reliability.

Table 3B: Existing Practices in Employee Selection process in NPA.

Formal employment testing procedures	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
The final selection test you did was relevant to my job.	4.48	Very unsatisfactory	1
You did a formal selection test before accessing this job.	4.47	Very unsatisfactory	2
You did an intelligence test to access this job.	4.23	Very unsatisfactory	3
The formal selection test examined your capacity to learn.	4.21	Very unsatisfactory	4
The formal selection test you did examined your abilities.	4.20	Unsatisfactory	5
The formal selection test examined your likes and dislikes.	3.93	Unsatisfactory	6
The formal selection test you did examined your traits.	3.90	Unsatisfactory	7
You did an aptitude test to access this job.	3.83	Unsatisfactory	8
You did a performance or achievement test to access this job	3.77	Unsatisfactory	9
You did a cognitive ability test to access this job.	3.66	Unsatisfactory	10
Sub Total	4.12	Unsatisfactory	
Physical or Medical examination procedure			
You did a health/medical fitness test before accessing this job.	3.87	Unsatisfactory	1

The health/medical examination was relevant to your job.	1.87	Satisfactory	2
Your health examination examined health and safety issues.	1.83	Satisfactory	3
The health/medical examination involved disabilities test.	1.63	Very satisfactory	4
Sub Total	2.30	Satisfactory	
Reference Checking procedure			
Your referees were contacted to give information about you.	4.33	Very Unsatisfactory	1
You were asked for referees before you accessed this job.	3.60	Fairly Satisfactory	2
Sub Total	3.97	Unsatisfactory	
Final approval			
You were given an appointment letter before starting this job.	4.87	Very Unsatisfactory	1
You believe the final selection and short listing of employees in NPA is fair and merit based.	4.47	Very Unsatisfactory	2
In NPA, there are clear follow-ups for new employees.	4.38	Very Unsatisfactory	3
In NPA , unsuccessful job applicants are always notified through letters or phone calls.	4.35	Very Unsatisfactory	4
Your appointment letter had a provision for job acceptance.	4.23	Very Unsatisfactory	5
Your appointment letter mentioned your special conditions like work, holidays, bonuses and fringe benefits.	3.98	Unsatisfactory	6
In NPA, the management or supervisors always check-up on the progress of new employees.	3.96	Unsatisfactory	7
In NPA, new employees are always well introduced in the organization to all old workers.	3.92	Unsatisfactory	8
introduces new employees to activities they are to do	3.27	Fairly Satisfactory	9
Your appointment letter mentioned your post, rank, and salary scale commencement date.	3.03	Fairly Satisfactory	10
Sub Total	4.05	Unsatisfactory	
Grand Total	3.45	Unsatisfactory	

Most components of the final approval procedure were evaluated as extremely poor, followed by unsatisfactory. Giving appointment letters before starting the work was the most disagreeable part of final approval, which the majority opposed to (mean=4.87). However, this would be a little ambiguous because one may ask if such an international organization could hire people without proper appointment letters. This response, on the other hand, might simply imply that appointment letters are not delivered on the first day of work because of things like probation, which many workers face, as shown in Table 1 of this chapter. As a result, even if employees are handed appointment letters, this occurs after they have started and finished their probation period. If a probationary employee is queried about his or her appointment letter while still on probation, he or she is likely to give the organization a bad rating. However, as mentioned in the previous section of this same aspect, the same respondents stated that their appointment letters contain information such as the position, rank, compensation scale, and start date. Only two components were regarded as satisfactory: exposing new workers to the tasks they are expected to accomplish (mean=3.27) and mentioning the employee's job, rank, and wage scale beginning date in appointment letters (mean=3.03). This finding suggests that employees are sent appointment letters late and so do not pay attention to them. Employees regarded the final selection process as disappointing on average (overall mean=4.05). An aggregate mean index (grand total) for all seven facets of selection was computed to gain a general picture of how good the available selection procedures in NPA are. This resulted in a mean of 3.45, confirming that the available selection methods in are not suitable.

Level of organization performance in case of NPA.

The study's dependent variable was organizational performance, which was split down into seven elements (including innovation and creativity, coordination, customer care, task completion, time keeping, quality maintenance and number of clients served).

All seven aspects of organizational performance were assessed using qualitative questions in the questionnaire, which were rated on a Likert scale of one to five; where 1 = strongly agree;

2 = Agree; 3 = Not sure; 4 = Disagree; 5 = strongly disagree. The following was used in the interpretation of their responses;

Rating Scale

<i>Answer Range</i>	<i>Response mode</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.00-1.80	strongly agree	very high performance
1.81-2.60	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	neutral	Medium
3.41-4.20	Disagree	low performance
4.21-5.00	strongly disagree	very low performance

Employees were asked to rate their company's performance on each of the elements in the table by checking the appropriate number in the associated box. As shown in table 3, their replies were evaluated using SPSS and presented using descriptive statistics displaying means.

Table 4 Level of Organization Performance in Case of NPA

	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Innovation and creativity			
The level of innovativeness in NPA is high.	3.93	low performance	1
The level of creativity in NPA is high.	3.39	Medium	2
The level of problem solving at work in NPA is high.	3.13	Medium	3
Sub Total	3.48	low performance	
Coordination			
The level of activities coordination in NPA is high.	3.85	low performance	1
The level of public confidence in the activities NPA of is high.	3.78	low performance	2
The level of cooperation among employees in NPA is high.	3.44	low performance	3
Sub Total	3.69	low performance	
Customer care			
In NPA, the quality of service to customers is very good.	4.37	very low performance	1
In NPA customers are treated very well.	4.00	low performance	2
The speed in responding to clients' needs & complaints is high	3.64	low performance	3
The dedication to improve customer service is high.	3.44	low performance	4
In NPA the speed in serving clients is high.	3.43	low performance	5
Sub Total	3.73	low performance	
Task completion			
In NPA tasks are always completed on time.	3.73	low performance	1
The level of completion in NPA is high.	3.53	low performance	2
In NPA all the relevant tasks are completed with quality.	3.03	Medium	3
Sub Total	3.43	low performance	
Time Management			
In NPA all task and activities are well time tabled.	3.93	low performance	1
In NPA decisions are always made quickly without delay.	3.91	low performance	2
In NPA planning of all activities done in time.	3.54	low performance	3
In NPA you have clear time saving measures.	3.52	low performance	4
In NPA there is a schedule showing activities to do & when.	3.47	low performance	5
In NPA you always meet deadlines and appointments.	3.45	low performance	6
In NPA most activities are always completed on time.	3.39	medium	7
Sub Total	3.60	low performance	
Quality maintenance			
In NPA you provide services that satisfy customer needs.	3.95	low performance	1
In NPA you provide error free services	3.50	low performance	2
In NPA You provide quality services to clients.	3.39	Medium	3
Sub Total	3.61	low performance	
Number of clients served			
The total numbers of clients you serve in a month is high	3.50	low performance	1
The numbers of clients you serve each day are so great.	3.43	low performance	2
The numbers of clients you serve in an hour is big.	1.63	very high	3
Sub total	2.85	Medium	
Overall Total	3.49	low performance	

The means in Table 4 show that workers judged the performance of on many criteria differently. For example, on one component of innovativeness (mean=3.93), was assessed as a poor performer, and as a medium performance on two aspects of degree of creativity in NPA (mean=3.39) and level of problem solving at work (mean=3.13). When we evaluate the mean for all three elements, it was regarded as a bad performance on the whole (3.48). This means that NPA has a lower level of originality and innovation. Employees are simply told what to do, with little space for them to experiment with their own methods. In terms of coordination, was assessed as a low performance on all three dimensions (mean=3.69), showing that activity coordination remains weak. On all of the items in the customer care category, it was evaluated as a poor performer, except for one, which was scored as a very low performance, and that was the quality of service offered to consumers (mean =4.73). This also suggests that NPA does not offer extra attention to consumers or clients, which might be due to the sort of staff, inadequate management, or uninspired employees. Only one component of task completion was assessed as a medium performance, and that was on doing relevant tasks with quality (mean= 3.03), with the rest being classified as bad. On a daily, weekly, monthly, quarterly, or yearly basis, the overall mean (3.43) on task completion was likewise low, meaning that there are many tasks left unfinished. This low level of job completion might be attributable to a variety of factors, including inadequate coordination, as mentioned earlier in this study, and poor staff abilities, among others. In terms of time management, it was assessed as a bad time manager in all areas except one, where it was rated as a mediocre performance (mean=3.39) for finishing activities on time. This shows that NPA wastes a significant amount of time. This also explains why the firm is underperforming in other areas, as time is crucial for every organization to meet its objectives. Respondents still evaluated quality maintenance as a low performer on two of the three things on the list. Only on the quality provision question did respondents assess themselves as a middling performer (mean=3.39). Finally, NPA workers demonstrated that their company performs poorly in terms of the number of clients serviced (overall mean=3.49). Employees, on the other hand, demonstrated that their organization's performance is medium (mean=2.85) in terms of the number of clients serviced in an hour. Employees demonstrated that their overall performance is low in terms of the quantity of clients served. The researcher computed an overall (Grand) mean for all factors in Table 3 to gain a final image of the level of performance at NPA, which came out to be 3.49, confirming that the level of performance at NPA was assessed as poor.

Relationship between Employee selection practices and Organizational performance in NPA.

The study's fourth goal was to see if there was a link between existing staff selection processes and organizational performance in the instance of NPA. The researcher proposed a null hypothesis, stating that there is no significant association between current personnel selection processes and NPA performance. To reach this last goal and test the null hypothesis, the researcher used the Pearson's Linear Correlation Coefficient to link the means for all characteristics of selection and those on performance, as shown in table 4 below.

Table 5: Pearson's Linear Correlation Coefficient Test results for Employee Selection Practices and Organizational Performance in NPA

Variables Correlated	r-value	Sig.	Interpretation	Decision on Ho
Selection Vs Innovation and Creativity	0.934	0.000	Significant correlation	Rejected
Selection Vs Coordination	0.938	0.000	Significant correlation	Rejected
Selection Vs Customer care	0.966	0.000	Significant correlation	Rejected
Selection Vs Task completion	0.953	0.000	Significant correlation	Rejected
Selection Vs Time management	0.955	0.000	Significant correlation	Rejected
Selection Vs Quality Maintenance	0.937	0.000	Significant correlation	Rejected
Selection Vs Number of Clients	0.944	0.000	Significant correlation	Rejected
Selection Vs Performance Index	0.956	0.000	Significant correlation	Rejected

In the instance of NPA (sig. 0.05), the results in Table 4 show that existing personnel selection methods are substantially connected with all dimensions of organizational performance. Employee selection processes are also favorably connected with all dimensions of organizational performance in NPA (r -values >0), according to the findings. According to this study, improving selection methods has a considerable impact on organizational success. The stated null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance based on these findings. Based on these findings, a change in the selection system, such as making it more relevant, transparent, and merit-based, is expected to increase NPA's performance by a coefficient of 0.956. (r -value on performance index). Although all areas of performance are highly connected with selection procedures, the component of customer care is the most important, with a correlation of 0.966 indicating that an improvement in choosing, say, customer care staff is likely to increase customer care services. Time management ($r=0.955$), task completion ($r=0.953$), and so on follow. The performance index was regressed against all seven characteristics of selection, the results of which are shown in table 5 below, to create a picture of how each selection method influences organizational performance.

TABLE 6: Regression Analysis between the Organizational Performance Index and Aspects of Employee Selection in NPA

Variables Regressed	Adjusted R ²	F-value	Sig.	Interpretation	Decision on Ho
Selection Vs Performance	.985	1366.868	0.000	Significant effect	Rejected
Coefficients	Beta	t	Sig.		
(Constant)		-3.932	.000	Significant	Rejected
Application	.562	7.128	.000	Significant	Rejected
Pre interview	-.526	-8.034	.000	Significant	Rejected
Final interview	-1.157	-11.468	.000	Significant	Rejected
Formal Employment Testing	.472	3.980	.000	Significant	Rejected
Medical Examination Tests	.544	8.126	.000	Significant	Rejected
Reference Checking	.575	9.593	.000	Significant	Rejected
Final approval	.659	6.134	.000	Significant	Rejected

The findings of the linear regression in Table 5 show that all seven elements together have a substantial impact on organizational success ($F=1366.868$, sig. =0.000). The findings show that in the instance of NPA, all seven elements of selection included in the regression model account for approximately 99 percent of variances in organizational performance (Adjusted R²=0.985). The coefficients part of this table shows how much each of the seven selection factors influences performance, as measured by Beta values. Final selection processes or practices, for example, have the greatest influence of all seven, with a beta value of 0.659, implying that final selection practices alone account for nearly 66 percent of differences in organizational performance. After that, there's reference checking (Beta=0.575), and so on. This indicates that, while organizations like NPA must enhance their selection methods, they should focus more on final approval, reference checks, application forms, and medical screening exams.

FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

FINDINGS

The following employee selection procedures were found to be unsatisfactory using descriptive statistics showing means: i) preliminary interview selection procedure (mean=3.67); ii) formal employment testing procedures (mean=4.12); iii) reference checking procedure (mean=3.97); and iv) final approval (mean=4.05). Employee selection procedures for: v) employee application forms selection method (mean=2.77); and vi) final selection interview procedure (mean=3.27) were considered to be reasonably good. Only one part of

personnel selection procedures, vii) Physical or Medical Examination Procedure (mean=2.30), was determined to be done satisfactorily. The overall mean index for all seven elements (overall mean=3.45) was deemed to be unacceptable. None of the seven were deemed acceptable or extremely acceptable. The results also showed that NPA's performance is poor in all of the areas studied, including i) innovation and originality (mean=3.48), ii) coordination (mean=3.69), iii) task completion (mean=3.43), iv) time management (mean=3.60), and v) quality maintenance (mean=3.61). Only one component of performance was given a medium rating: the number of clients serviced (mean=2.85). Employee selection processes in NPA are strongly and positively connected with the following characteristics of performance, according to Pearson's Linear Correlation Coefficient results; i) Innovation and Creativity ($r = 0.934$, sig. = 0.000); ii) Coordination ($r = 0.938$, sig. = 0.000); iii) Customer care ($r = 0.966$, sig. = 0.000); iv) Task completion ($r = 0.953$, sig. = 0.000); v) Time management ($r = 0.955$, sig. = 0.000); vi) Quality Maintenance ($r = 0.937$, sig. = 0.000); and vii) Number of Clients ($r = 0.944$, sig. = 0.000). Regression analysis results indicated that of all the seven aspects of employee selection practices, the aspect of final approval (Beta=0.659), by reference checking (Beta=0.575), application forms procedure (Beta=.562) and Medical Examination Tests (Beta=0.544) have a bigger effect on organizational performance compared to the rest. On the overall, all the seven aspects of employee selection practices explain almost 99% towards variations in the performance of NPA.

CONCLUSIONS

The researcher draws a conclusion to the study findings in connection to the study goals stated in this part. The researcher finds that staff selection methods in NPA are still inadequate in general, and that they all need to be improved, based on the findings of the fourth aim. Formal employment testing processes are the most disappointing, followed by the final approval phase. The researcher concludes from the findings of the third objective that NPA's performance is still low, and that this is due in part to the organization's bad selection methods. Customer service, coordination, and time management are the poorest aspects of performance. They explain why the overall performance of is bad because they are essential parts of every company. The fourth objective's findings revealed a positive significant relationship between all seven aspects of selection and all aspects of organizational performance, leading to the conclusion that the more transparent selection processes are in an organization and the more prospective employees are selected on merit, the higher the organization's overall performance will be, and vice versa. The findings of the regression analysis revealed that all seven aspects of employee selection together contribute over 98 percent to variations in organization ('s) performance, leading to the conclusion that a one percent improvement in employee selection practices is likely to increase an organization's performance by 0.985 percent, almost a one-to-one contribution. As a result, if NPA wants to enhance its performance, it must realize that the better the staff selection methods are at NPA, the better the performance will be, and vice versa. Even if all selection methods and practices have a considerable impact on an organization's success when taken collectively, not all seven variables have the same impact. Some have a greater impact than others, and the researcher finds that the final approval phase is the most essential component of selection in this study. Even if all of the previous procedures are completed satisfactorily, if the final approval is not handled with care, the selected workers may not be able to contribute significantly to increasing organizational performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the study aims and hypothesis, this part deals with suggestions emerging from the study findings and conclusions. Based on the findings of the second aim, the researcher advises that the following be done to enhance the effectiveness of the NPA, Juba - Southern Sudan program:

a) NPA management should strengthen the employee application form selection method to guarantee that workers with higher performance skills are chosen. For example, application forms should inquire about an employee's talents, credentials, specialities, and experiences, and the information provided on the form should be relevant to the position being applied for. The hiring procedure should also be made more equitable so that the bank can hire the greatest performers. Based on the findings of the second hypothesis, the researcher suggests that, in order to increase employee performance in the NPA, Juba - Southern Sudan program, the following should be addressed about the job interview technique of selection:

b) The management of NPA should try to improve the employee interviews selection procedure so as to ensure that workers with more performance abilities are selected. For example, there should be both preliminary and final selection interviews. In the preliminary interviews, workers should be asked about company profile, the profile of the job they are applying for, examine their morale and confidence, their technical abilities, their written and oral abilities and other questions relevant to the respective jobs. Where possible final interviews should be face-to-face and panel based. The questions asked should not be very hard nor very easy, should be clear not ambiguous and should be designed from the job aspects one is applying for. Basing on the findings of the fourth objective, the researcher recommends that for employee performance in NPA to be improved, the following should be noted as regards to formal employment testing procedure of selection;

c) Organizations like NPA should put their focus on other ways of screening the best employees and should not over rely on formal test. For example examining employee traits, abilities, likes and dislikes, capacity to learn, intelligence levels and performance or achievement using formal tests should be done in other ways other than formal test. For example, practical tests relating to these aspects may be used. Also basing on the findings of the fourth objective, the researcher recommends that if NPA is to select employee with high performance abilities, the following should be noted as regards to Physical examination and Reference checking procedure of selection;

d) Organizations like NPA should put their focus on other ways of screening the best employees other than over relying on physical examination and reference checking. For example, information on employee disabilities, their feelings over organizational legal issues, health and safety policies and information from their referees, may not help select good workers and so NPA should not over rely on.

Areas for Further Research

In the due process of writing this thesis, the researcher could not tackle all the problem areas under selection process and organization performance and this therefore leaves a lot to be researched on especially in areas like tests used in selecting new employees, types of interviews used in sieving out the best applicants, linkage between recruitment and selection, selection policies and legal issues in selection process. Therefore, a compressive study by anyone who might be interested in investigating more about selection process is recommendable in the fore mentioned topics highlighted by the researcher.

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